

CLINICAL IVD eCRF CONSENSUS

SECTION 1: DEMOGRAPHICS

- **Subject fiscal code**
- **Visit date**
- **Birth date**
- **Age**
- **Sex**
- **Years of education**
- **Level of education**
- **Main occupation**
- **Is the subject currently working?**
 - **If not, when did the subject retire?**
- **Marital status**
- **With whom does the subject live**
- **Handedness**
- **Who is the informant**
- **Demographics note**

SECTION 2: CLINICAL HISTORY

- **Is cognitive decline reported by the subject?**
- **Is cognitive decline reported by the informant?**
- **Based on clinical judgment, the subject presents the following cognitive symptoms:**
 - no cognitive symptoms
 - memory disturbance
 - spatial disorientation
 - temporal disorientation
 - language disturbance
 - apraxia
 - prosopagnosia
 - attention deficit
 - executive deficits
 - visuospatial disturbances
 - acute confusional state
 - cognitive fluctuations
 - other
- **Are psychopathological symptoms/behavioral alterations reported by the subject?**
- **Are psychopathological symptoms/behavioral alterations reported by the informant?**
- **Based on clinical judgment, the subject presents the following psychopathological symptoms/behavioral alterations:**
 - no psychopathological symptoms
 - anxiety
 - depression
 - apathy
 - fatuousness

- disinhibition
- irritability
- agitation
- aggressiveness
- fixed ideas/delusions
- visual hallucinations
- acoustic hallucinations
- REM sleep behaviour disorder
- other sleep disturbances
- gluttony
- changes in food preferences
- other changes in eating habits
- anosognosia
- **Are motor symptoms reported by the subject?**
- **Are motor symptoms reported by the informant?**
- **Based on clinical judgment, the subject presents the following motor symptoms:**
 - no motor symptoms
 - gait disturbance (not due to osteoarthritis or previous trauma)
 - repeated falls
 - tremor
 - hypokinesia/bradykinesia (including hypomimia)
 - postural instability
- **Cognitive symptoms at onset:**
 - no cognitive symptoms
 - memory disturbance
 - spatial disorientation
 - temporal disorientation
 - language disturbance
 - apraxia
 - prosopagnosia
 - attention deficit
 - executive deficits
 - visuospatial disturbances
 - acute confusional state
 - cognitive fluctuations
 - other
- **Psychopathological symptoms/behavioral alterations at onset:**
 - no psychopathological symptoms
 - anxiety
 - depression
 - apathy
 - fatuousness
 - disinhibition
 - irritability
 - agitation
 - aggressiveness
 - fixed ideas/delusions
 - visual hallucinations

- acoustic hallucinations
- REM sleep behavior disorder
- other sleep disturbances
- gluttony
- changes in food preferences
- other changes in eating habits
- anosognosia
- **Motor symptoms at onset**
 - no motor symptoms
 - gait disturbance (not due to osteoarthritis or previous trauma)
 - repeated falls
 - tremor
 - hypokinesia/bradykinesia (including hypomimia)
 - postural instability
- **Year of onset of cognitive symptoms, if present**
- **Year of onset of psychopathological symptoms/behavioral alterations, if present**
- **Year of onset of motor symptoms, if present**
- **If motor symptoms can be referred to as parkinsonism, did they appear more than 12 months before the onset of cognitive symptoms?**
- **Has the diagnosis been made before?**
- **If yes, what was the diagnosis?**
- **If yes, what was the year of the first diagnosis?**
- **Mode of onset of the disease**
 - insidious
 - subacute
 - acute
 - undetermined
- **Disease course**
 - slow progression
 - slow progression with fluctuations in alertness or attention
 - stepwise worsening
 - rapid progression
 - stability
 - improvement
- **Diagnostic hypotheses**
- **Clinical history notes**

SECTION 3: RISK FACTORS

- **Number of sisters**
- **Number of brothers**
- **Does the subject have a family history of dementia?**
 - **If yes, which relative, and when was the onset age?**
- **Does the subject have a family history of Parkinson's disease?**
 - **If yes, which relative, and when was the onset age?**
- **Does the subject have a family history of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis?**
 - **If yes, which relative, and when was the onset age?**

- **Does the subject have a family history of psychiatric disorder?**
 - If yes, which relative, and what disorder?
- **Does the subject practice physical activity?**
 - If yes, which one? And how many times per week?
- **Does the subject smoke?**
- **Risk factors notes**

SECTION 4: COMORBIDITY

- **Current comorbidity/risk factors**
 - arterial hypertension
 - dyslipidemia
 - ischemic heart disease
 - dilated cardiomyopathy/heart failure
 - atrial fibrillation
 - osteoporosis
 - osteoarthritis
 - epilepsy
 - diabetes mellitus
 - malignant tumor
 - thyroid disease
 - hepatic insufficiency
 - chronic kidney disease
 - respiratory insufficiency
 - chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)
 - gastric disease
 - intestinal disease
 - peripheral neuropathy
 - infectious diseases
 - low visual acuity
 - hypoacusis
- **Past comorbidity/risk factors**
 - stroke
 - TIA
 - head trauma
 - arterial hypertension
 - malignant tumor
 - ischemic heart disease
 - dilated cardiomyopathy/heart failure
 - atrial fibrillation
 - epilepsy
 - diabetes mellitus
 - thyroid disease
 - hepatic insufficiency
 - chronic kidney disease
 - respiratory insufficiency
 - infectious diseases

- **History of psychiatric disorders**
 - depression
 - psychosis
 - anxiety
 - alcohol abuse
- **Comorbidity notes**

SECTION 5: OBJECTIVE EXAM

- **Height [cm]**
- **Weight [kg]**
- **Body mass index**
- **Unintentional weights loss (more than 4.5 kg in the last 6 months)**
- **Systolic pressure [mmHg]**
- **Diastolic pressure [mmHg]**
- **Orthostatic hypotension**
- **Neurological examination**
 - **Alertness/consciousness**
 - normal
 - altered (e.g., delirium)
 - **Language**
 - normal
 - fluent aphasia
 - non-fluent aphasia
 - apraxia of speech
 - dysarthria
 - hypophonia
 - **Ideomotor praxis**
 - normal
 - altered
 - **Visual acuity**
 - normal
 - reduced in right eye
 - reduced in left eye
 - **Visual field**
 - normal
 - right hemianopia
 - left hemianopia
 - **Extraocular movements**
 - eyelid apraxia

- slowness of saccades
- limitation of upward gaze
- limitation of downward gaze
- limitation of horizontal gaze
- **Remaining cranial nerves**
 - right facial nerve weakness
 - left facial nerve weakness
 - right facial nerve weakness (lower face only)
 - left facial nerve weakness (lower face only)
 - dysphagia
 - dysphonia
 - dysarthria
 - right hypoglossal palsy
 - left hypoglossal palsy
- **Frontal release signs**
 - absent
 - glabellar sign
 - palmo-mental sign
 - snout reflex
- **Stance**
 - normal
 - oscillations
 - impossible
- **Romberg**
 - negative
 - positive
- **Gait**
 - normal
 - apraxic (magnetic gait, with reduced stride length and widened base)
 - ataxic
 - parkinsonian
 - right hemiparetic
 - left hemiparetic
 - paraparetic
 - other (e.g., altered due to non-neurologic causes such as osteoarthritic pain)
- **Muscle mass**
 - normal
 - reduced
- **Muscle tone**
 - normal

- neck rigidity
- axial rigidity
- rigidity of right upper limb
- rigidity of left upper limb
- rigidity of right lower limb
- rigidity of left lower limb
- spasticity of right upper limb
- spasticity of left upper limb
- spasticity of right lower limb
- spasticity of left lower limb
- **Test of upper limb antigravity strength (Mingazzini test for the upper limbs)**
 - normal
 - right weakness
 - left weakness
- **Test of lower limb antigravity strength (Mingazzini test for the lower limbs)**
 - normal
 - right weakness
 - left weakness
- **Global motility**
 - normal
 - bradykinesia
- **Segmental motility**
 - normal
 - bradykinesia of right upper limb
 - bradykinesia of left upper limb
 - bradykinesia of right lower limb
 - bradykinesia of left lower limb
- **Involuntary movements**
 - absent
 - head tremor at rest
 - right upper limb tremor at rest
 - left upper limb tremor at rest
 - right lower limb tremor at rest
 - left lower limb tremor at rest
 - action/postural tremor of right upper limb
 - action/postural tremor of left upper limb
 - myoclonus of right upper limb
 - myoclonus of left upper limb
 - myoclonus of right lower limb
 - myoclonus of left lower limb
 - fasciculations of right upper limb
 - fasciculations of left upper limb

- fasciculations of right lower limb
- fasciculations of left lower limb
- **Deep tendon reflexes**
 - normal
 - symmetrically decreased/absent
 - asymmetrically decreased/absent
 - symmetrically increased
 - asymmetrically increased
- **Pyramidal signs**
 - absent
 - extensor plantar response on the right
 - extensor plantar response of the left
 - Hoffmann's sign on the right
 - Hoffmann's sign on the left
- **Sensation**
 - Normal
 - cortical sensory deficit of right upper limb
 - cortical sensory deficit of left upper limb
 - extinction of bilateral tactile stimulus
- **Sphincters**
 - normal
 - stress urinary incontinence
 - urge urinary incontinence
 - fecal incontinence
- **Neurological examination notes**

SECTION 6: DRUGS

- **Drug therapy at the time of the visit**
- **Recommended drug therapy at discharge**
- **Discharge date**
- **Drugs notes**